

or translated into higher yields. Early vigor was probably sacrificed to ensure a better canopy structure at the late growth stages and better partitioning of photosynthates to grain. This was well exhibited by the hybrids, especially MTUHR2033, MTUHR2020, and MTUHR2037, which had significantly higher grain yields. These hybrids also recorded greater BMP and HI. Though the check varieties and hybrids did not differ for BMP, the hybrids showed a superior performance because of more grains per panicle, which was indicated by a higher HI. Two hybrids, MTUHR2024 and MTUHR2029, however, showed an inferior performance compared with the best check Chaitanya in BMP, HI, and grain yield.

Heterosis is a highly cross-specific phenomenon. To use heterosis successfully to increase grain yield, parental genotypes need to be selected from modern cultivars with a high potential. The physiological efficiency of F_1 hybrids at the vegetative stage is a useful indication of heterosis for grain yield. MTUHR2033 and MTUHR2020, which showed such physiological efficiency, hold good promise. ■

Performance of hybrid rice in south Karnataka

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At the agricultural research stations at Honnaville and Kathalagere, we evaluated elite hybrids. We also investigated the fixing of isolation distance, number of seedlings to be planted hill⁻¹, and N management. Among the various hybrids tested in 1991-94, IR58025A / IR9761-19-1R was found to be superior to inbred variety Mangala. This hybrid recorded an average yield of 5.6 and 4.9 t ha⁻¹, respectively, at Honnaville and Kathalagere. Mangala yielded 3.8 and 3.6 t ha⁻¹, respectively, at those two centers. This hybrid also performed well in on-farm trials in the districts of Chikamagalore, Hassan, Mysore, and Shimoga, with a mean grain yield of 5.9 t ha⁻¹ vs 4.7 t ha⁻¹ for Mangala. This hybrid was named Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and released for general cultivation in the southern transition zone.

Similarly, another F_1 hybrid, IR58025A / KMR 3, had an average yield of 6.6 t ha⁻¹ vs 5.1 t ha⁻¹ for Jaya. This hybrid was found promising because it matured in 125-130 d, similar to the popular inbred variety. In 12 on-farm trials, this hybrid registered a mean grain yield of 7.3 t ha⁻¹ vs 6.0 t ha⁻¹ for the standard check Jaya. This hybrid was named Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 and released for general cultivation in 1996. The present recommended dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹ for the varieties was found to be equally effective for the two hybrids. There was no difference in yield among plots planted with one, two, three, four, or five seedlings hill⁻¹ in both the dry and wet seasons. Tillering ability in the hybrids was found to be very good. Therefore, planting 1 seedling hill⁻¹ ensured an economical seed input cost. In the studies conducted on isolation distance, seed set decreased with every increase in the isolation distance. This called for a revision of isolation distance for each hybrid through investigations at specific locations. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of salinity on growth, chlorophyll content, and flag leaf area of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) genotypes

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Rice is the most important food crop, feeding more than half of the world's population. To feed this ever-growing population, an increase in the cultivation of food crops is essential, which is possible by increasing cultivable lands.

Lands in Pakistan that are available for cultivation suffer from problems of

salinity / sodicity. So we urgently need to select or develop salt-tolerant rice varieties or methods to increase the yield per unit area.

Although yield is the result of interactions in the genetic makeup of genotypes, it has been suggested that by increasing photosynthetic efficiency, crop production could be increased (Ashraf et al 1995). Photosynthetic efficiency depends on leaf area, chlorophyll content, stomatal response, gas exchange, etc. We therefore used a physiological-genetic approach to test whether genotypes sensitive to or tolerant of salt differ in their photosynthetic efficiency.

For this purpose, a gravel culture experiment was conducted in a growth cabinet maintained at 30/25 + 2 °C day / night temperature and a photoperiod of 10 h, to study the effect of salinity created by mixed salt (Na_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 , MgCl_2 , and NaCl in the ratio of 6.33:3.58:1:2.28) and NaCl only on growth and photosynthetic activity of rice genotypes. Thirty-day-old seedlings of five rice genotypes—BH-5-89, BH-3-89, RST-1-86, RST-2-84, and Bas370×NR1—were acquired from the rice section of the Mutation Breeding Division of the NIAB, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

This experiment consisted of five treatments (0, 5, and 10 dS m⁻¹ EC prepared with mixed salt and EC 5, 10 dS m⁻¹ with NaCl only) with three replications in a completely randomized block design. The plants were sown in plastic pots (30 cm diam and 25 cm length) filled with washed gravel containing full-strength Hoagland solution. The treatments were prepared by adding salt solutions from 2.5 dS m⁻¹ and maintained at desired concentrations. This was done to prevent sudden shock to the plant from salinity. The volume of the solution was maintained daily by adding Hoagland solution. The plants were harvested after 1 mo and their dry weight plant⁻¹ (after drying the plants in an oven at 70 °C for 72 h), flag leaf area (Ashraf et al 1995), and chlorophyll content (Arnon 1949) were estimated.

The results indicated that biomass decreased with an increase in salt concentration in all the genotypes except at 5 dS m⁻¹ of mixed salt, where enhancement was recorded in rice genotype BH-3-89 (Table 1). The maximum reduction in biomass was under 10 dS m⁻¹ (NaCl). In BH-5-89, Bas370XNR1, and BH-3-89, the reduction in biomass at 10 dS m⁻¹ (NaCl) was less than 50%. On the other hand, RST-1-86 and RST-2-84 had a biomass of only 31 and 33% that of the control under the same treatment. Similar genotypic differences have been reported for rice, sorghum, and wheat.

A reduction in flag leaf area was observed in all the genotypes with increases in salt concentration (Table 1). The maximum decrease was again under 10 dS m⁻¹ (NaCl). The genotypes with a higher biomass had a higher flag leaf area (Table 1). The minimum flag leaf area was recorded for RST-1-86 and RST-2-84, and with mixed salt. Hussain and Ismail (1994) also reported a reduction in leaf area caused by salinity in sunflower.

The chlorophyll content (a, b, and total) of rice leaves was generally reduced by salinity (Table 2). RST-1-86

Table 1. Effect of different salinity levels on biomass (dry matter plant⁻¹) and flag leaf area (cm²) of different rice genotypes.

Treatment (dS m ⁻¹)	Genotypes				
	BH-5-89	BH-3-89	RST-1-86	RST-2-84	Bas370XNR1
0 (control)					
DM ^a	2.29 (100) ^b	2.31 (100)	4.53 (100)	3.45 (100)	3.88 (100)
LA	16.60 (100)	20.62 (100)	36.67 (100)	22.31 (100)	21.87 (100)
5 (mixed salt)					
DM	2.11 (92)	3.58 (154)	4.41 (97)	3.57 (103)	3.09 (74)
LA	13.80 (83)	18.60 (90)	21.19 (58)	19.35 (86)	13.72 (63)
10 (mixed salt)					
DM	1.69 (74)	2.04 (83)	2.23 (43)	1.37 (34)	2.44 (63)
LA	10.30 (62)	15.41 (75)	17.90 (44)	8.37 (38)	12.75 (54)
5 (NaCl)					
DM	2.01 (88)	2.09 (90)	2.35 (52)	2.59 (75)	2.96 (63)
LA	10.26 (61)	13.05 (63)	14.27 (34)	11.47 (51)	13.10 (54)
10 (NaCl)					
DM	1.54 (67)	1.68 (54)	1.42 (31)	1.36 (33)	2.10 (54)
LA	6.30 (38)	4.26 (21)	4.77 (13)	4.11 (18)	10.52 (43)

^aDM = dry matter (g plant⁻¹), LA = flag leaf area (cm²). ^bValues in parentheses show % of control.

Table 2. Effect of different levels of salinity on chlorophyll (a, b, and total) (mg g⁻¹ fresh weight) of different rice genotypes.

Treatment (dS m ⁻¹)	Genotypes				
	BH-5-89	BH-3-89	RST-1-86	RST-2-84	Bas370XNR1
0 (control)					
Chl a ^a	0.424 (100) ^b	0.427 (100)	0.299 (100)	0.383 (100)	0.397 (100)
Chl b	0.486 (100)	0.494 (100)	0.517 (100)	0.490 (100)	0.424 (100)
Chl t	0.910 (100)	0.921 (100)	0.816 (100)	0.873 (100)	0.821 (100)
5 (mixed salt)					
Chl a	0.407 (96)	0.412 (95)	0.299 (100)	0.302 (74)	0.399 (101)
Chl b	0.438 (90)	0.496 (100)	0.481 (64)	0.481 (98)	0.443 (104)
Chl t	0.845 (93)	0.908 (99)	0.781 (89)	0.783 (90)	0.842 (103)
10 (mixed salt)					
Chl a	0.360 (85)	0.367 (86)	0.233 (78)	0.297 (77)	0.389 (98)
Chl b	0.382 (79)	0.476 (76)	0.261 (35)	0.440 (90)	0.418 (99)
Chl t	0.742 (82)	0.743 (81)	0.494 (57)	0.737 (84)	0.807 (98)
5 (NaCl)					
Chl a	0.403 (95)	0.384 (84)	0.289 (96)	0.262 (63)	0.392 (99)
Chl b	0.411 (85)	0.424 (86)	0.406 (54)	0.364 (74)	0.384 (91)
Chl t	0.814 (89)	0.808 (88)	0.695 (80)	0.626 (72)	0.776 (94)

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Table 2 continued.

Treatment (dS m ⁻¹)	Genotypes				
	BH-5-89	BH-3-89	RST-1-86	RST-2-84	Bas370XNR-1
10 (NaCl)					
Chl a	0.300 (71)	0.310 (73)	0.163 (54)	0.222 (58)	0.357 (90)
Chl b	0.370 (76)	0.405 (62)	0.172 (23)	0.297 (61)	0.354 (83)
Chl t	0.670 (74)	0.615 (67)	0.335 (39)	0.519 (59)	0.711 (87)

^aChl a = chlorophyll a, Chl b = chlorophyll b, Chl t = chlorophyll (total). ^bValues in parentheses show % of control.

and RST-2-84 had the lowest chlorophyll content of the five genotypes.

Biomass production is a function of photosynthetic efficiency (Terry and Waldron 1984), which is decreased because of the decrease in leaf area and chlorophyll. A decrease in leaf area causes a reduction in area for light

interception and absorption of the specific wavelength necessary for photosynthesis. The results of this experiment showed that NaCl is more toxic and injurious than mixed salts and that BH-5-89, BH-3-89, and Bas370 are more tolerant of salt stress and RST-1-86 and RST-2-84 are sensitive to salt stress.

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Crop management

A labor-saving technique in direct-sown and transplanted rice

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The Cauvery Delta zone accounts for about 22.3% of the rice area and 25.3% of rice production in Tamil Nadu State. Rice is cultivated in three distinct seasons—*kuruwai* (Jun-Oct), followed by *thaladi* (Oct-Feb) in double-crop

wetlands and *samba* (Sep-Jan) in single-crop wetlands.

Transplanting continues to be the major method of crop establishment for rice in this area. It requires more labor, time, and efforts. The scarcity and high cost of farm labor invariably delay transplanting and often lead to the use of aged seedlings. Uncertain release of water from the Mettur dam aggravates the situation for seedling age and time of transplanting.

Because of these problems, many rice farmers wish to switch to direct seeding under puddled conditions.

Besides reducing labor requirements, it can help to shorten the growth cycle from seeding to maturity. Experiments were conducted during 1995-96 and 1996-97 at the TNRRI to evaluate wet seeding for establishing rice crops.

The methods of crop establishment—transplanting (S1), sowing sprouted seeds in lines manually (S2), and using a seed drum (S3)—were compared. The drum seeder used in this trial was developed by the Department of Agricultural Engineering, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore. The 8-row drum seeder

Table 1. Effect of crop establishment methods on yield and economics of rice, 1995-96.

Treatment	Days to 50% flowering		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Net return (Rs ha ⁻¹)		Return Re ⁻¹ invested	
	Kuruwai ^a	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi
Transplanting (S1)	85.8	105.6	5.5	4.8	6.6	5.1	16,165	11,982	2.32	1.98
Sowing sprouted seeds in lines manually (S2)	78.6	98.6	5.5	4.9	6.7	5.3	16,561	13,545	2.47	2.20
Drum seeding of sprouted seeds (S3)	78.9	98.7	5.6	5.0	6.8	5.3	17,836	13,960	2.65	2.29
CD (P = 0.05)	0.62	0.55	ns ^b	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.204	ns

^aKuruwai = Jun-Oct, thaladi = Oct-Feb. ^bns = not significant.